

Domestic Energy Service Business Models: Insights from the PROSEU project

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Summary of PROSEU

PROSEU aims to mainstream the renewable energy Prosumer phenomenon in the European Energy Union. Prosumers are active energy users who both consume and produce energy from renewable sources (RES). The growth of RES Prosumerism all over Europe challenges current energy market structures and institutions. PROSEU's research focuses on collectives of RES Prosumers and will investigate new business models, market regulations, infrastructural integration, technology scenarios and energy policies across Europe. The team will collaborate with RES Prosumer Initiatives (Living Labs), policymakers and other stakeholders from nine countries, following a quasi-experimental approach to learn how RES Prosumer communities, start-ups and businesses are dealing with their own challenges, and to determine what incentive structures will enable the mainstreaming of RES Prosumerism, while safeguarding citizen participation, inclusiveness and transparency. Moving beyond a case by case and fragmented body of research on RES Prosumers, PROSEU will build an integrated knowledge framework for a socio-political, socioeconomic, business and financial, technological, socio-technical and socio-cultural understanding of RES Prosumerism and coalesce in a comprehensive identification and assessment of incentive structures to enable the process of mainstreaming RES Prosumers in the context of the energy transition.

Summary of PROSEU's Objectives

Eight key objectives at the foundation of the project's vision and work plan:

- **Objective 1:** Document and analyse the current state of the art with respect to (150-200) RES Prosumer initiatives in Europe.
- **Objective 2:** Identify and analyse the regulatory frameworks and policy instruments relevant for RES Prosumer initiatives in nine participating Member States.
- **Objective 3:** Identify innovative financing schemes throughout the nine participating Member States and the barriers and opportunities for RES Prosumer business models.
- **Objective 4:** Develop scenarios for 2030 and 2050 based on in-depth analysis of technological solutions for RES Prosumers under different geographical, climatic and socio-political conditions.
- **Objective 5:** Discuss the research findings with 30 relevant stakeholders in a Participatory Integrated Assessment and produce a roadmap (until 2030 and 2050) for mainstreaming RE Prosumerism.
- **Objective 6:** Synthesise the lessons learned through experimentation and co-learning within and across Living Labs.
- **Objective 7:** Develop new methodological tools and draw lessons on how the PROSEU methodology, aimed at co-creation and learning, can itself serve as an experiment with institutional innovation.
- **Objective 8:** Create an RES Prosumer Community of Interest.

PROSEU Consortium Partners

Logo	Organisation	Type	Country
FCiências^{ID} <small>ASSOCIAÇÃO PARA A INVESTIGAÇÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO DE CIÊNCIAS</small>	FCIENCIAS.ID	Private non-profit association	Portugal
U.PORTO <small>FEUP FACULDADE DE ENGENHARIA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO</small>	U.PORTO	University	Portugal
ICLEI <small>Local Governments for Sustainability</small>	ICLEI EURO	Small and medium-sized enterprise	Germany
ClientEarth	CLIENTEARTH	Non-governmental organisation	United Kingdom
UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	UNIVLEEDS	University	United Kingdom
drift for transition	DRIFT	University	the Netherlands
FSB	UNIZAGFSB	University	Croatia
LEUPHANA <small>UNIVERSITÄT LÖNEBURG</small>	LEUPHANA	University	Germany
eco-union	ECO-UNION	Non-governmental organisation	Spain
i ö w <small>INSTITUTE FOR ECOLOGICAL ECONOMY RESEARCH</small>	IÖW	Private non-profit limited company	Germany
40 CE Delft <small>Committed to the Environment</small>	CE Delft	Small and medium-sized enterprise	the Netherlands

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Executive Summary

Context

- Decarbonisation of UK buildings has stalled and emissions from the sector have increased in recent years
- New homes currently being built will need retrofitting to meet 2050 climate targets
- There is a significant performance gap between modelled and actual energy performance of new homes
- 80% of homes in 2050 will be those already standing – meaning retrofit is the bigger challenge, although low hanging fruit have largely been exploited
- Heat decarbonisation is a huge challenge, with no directly transferable solution
- Existing business models of housebuilding, energy supply and domestic retrofit are poorly suited to this challenge

Energy as a service business models

- Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) may present a solution, by shifting incentives and profits away from selling volumes of energy towards selling useful services
- The models can be defined by their *scope* – meaning the number of services covered in the contract, and their *depth* – meaning the extent to which ESCOs have control over final conversion equipment
- These models are increasingly viable in a domestic setting - due to reducing transaction costs of modelling, metering and monitoring and ‘internet of things’ enabled devices

Findings from workshop

- Energy as a service models have the potential to deliver real performance outcomes, offer a simple and compelling customer offer and provide secure returns for finance providers
- These models will also help to integrate low cost but intermittent renewable electricity with other energy vectors such as heat, as well as demand side flexibility although require interoperable systems, aggregators and new regulation
- Deeper and broader service models have higher transaction costs and face a number of barriers to adoption
- Our workshop highlighted how new homes can be an easier first market for these business models
- These longer term models require trust; with the role of government, local authorities and community groups essential in building trust
- The UK’s supply chain, especially SMEs, are not well adapted to this market and there is currently a major skills and knowledge gap
- Regulation also lags behind and there are also significant regulatory overlaps between, energy building and financial regulation that need addressing coherently for this market to flourish
- Government needs to intervene to offer low cost, long term patient finance, if the existing housing stock is to be upgraded in line with 2050 targets

1. Introduction

1.1 Objectives of this report

Buildings, and especially homes, are the largest single consumer of energy and producer of greenhouse gas (CO₂e) emissions in most advanced economies [1]. In the UK and other nations with cold/temperate climates, the bulk of this energy consumption and CO₂e emissions result from space heating and hot water consumption [2]. Although electricity systems in countries such as the UK are decarbonising; energy demand from internal appliance use is increasing, heat systems are electrifying and electric vehicles are being adopted at an exponential rate [3]. Therefore, the significance of domestic heat consumption and increasing demand for electricity, places buildings and especially homes at the centre of the sustainable energy transition.

To meet ambitious climate change mitigation targets - as set out in the Energy Performance in Buildings Directive (EPBD) and in the UK's legally binding Carbon Budgets - emissions from homes must be drastically reduced by 2030, and near eliminated by 2050 [4,5]. This challenge means new homes must meet near zero energy standards (NZEB), existing homes must to be retrofitted to the highest standards of energy efficiency and heating systems must transition to low/zero carbon sources. Emissions from homes¹ can be reduced by three types of measure: **energy efficiency and airtightness** improvements to the building fabric; the adoption of **low carbon heating, ventilation and cooling** technologies (HVAC); and **electricity microgeneration** such as solar photovoltaics (PV) – where households become renewable energy ‘prosumers’

New homes are ostensibly the easiest place to make progress, however, several factors contribute to the limited penetration of zero carbon/energy homes in countries such as the UK. Chief among these is the lack of a strong regulatory environment for new homes. UK plans for a mandatory Zero Carbon Homes standard were scrapped - in part due to resistance from the construction industry – citing the additional costs of building to these higher standards [6]. At the same time, new homes are plagued by a ‘performance gap’ of energy efficiency measures – where modelled energy demand is not matched by measured performance [7].

Further, the most savings must be found in existing homes – with 80% of the UK's homes in 2050 expected to be those already standing. Therefore, energy efficiency, low carbon heat and microgeneration measures must be installed to millions of existing homes in the coming decades. Thus far, savings have been achieved through incremental measures, such as fluorescent lightbulbs, loft insulation and efficient boilers [8]. However, it is increasingly recognised that this approach will be insufficient to meet climate change targets [1,9]. Instead, increasing emphasis is on ‘whole-house retrofits’ involving multiple measures, new heating systems and integrated renewable energy and storage. However, progress in retrofitting the existing housing stock has been abysmal in recent years – with emissions from buildings actually increasing in the UK in 2017-18 [9].

These issues have led researchers and practitioners to explore new business models to overcome these interrelated challenges [10]. One concept is to shift the business model of energy provision away from

¹ These physical measures do not include the potential of behaviour/social practice changes

energy supply towards *energy services*. Here, instead of paying for units of energy (kWh) customers instead pay for useful energy services (heat, light, cooling etc) - shifting the responsibility for efficiency away from individual households and onto energy service companies (ESCOs).

In this report we explore these issues through a series of ‘energy-as-a-service’ case studies culminating in a stakeholder workshop in the city of Bristol, UK on the 6th of December 2019. This workshop brought together key stakeholders in this emerging space, to explore how these business models could be applied to 1) new housing, 2) low carbon heat systems and 3) whole house retrofits. The remainder of this document sets out these examples drawing on the findings of the workshop as well as a series of semi-structured interviews conducted between 2017-2020.

1.2 Energy service business models – theory and practice

The concept of the ‘business model’ has gained widespread use: as a means of classifying different businesses, a lens for academic research and as an entrepreneurial tool for practitioners [11]. Increasingly, the vital role of the business model in the diffusion of technological innovations [12,13] and in energy transitions [14,15] is being acknowledged. This has led to a focus on ‘business model innovation’ as an important area for both incumbent and entrepreneurial firms [16], in promoting sustainability, and in addressing climate change [17,18].

Business models describe the nature of value delivered to customers, how organisations and networks create value and the means of capturing revenues from that value [19,20]. Whilst the energy studies field focusses primarily on technologies, there is growing recognition of the integral role of accompanying business models, particularly for the radical, ground-breaking or ‘systemic’ innovations which characterise energy transitions [21].

Energy service business models guarantee consumers/prosumers receive the final energy service such as: reliable electricity, hot water, and stable room temperatures, rather than selling a specific technology or energy commodity (units of electricity, gas, oil etc). These models shift the responsibility for the performance of the building into long-term contracts between the ESCO and the household/business [22]. Solar-as-a-service models help households become ‘prosumers’ without the upfront cost. Here, the ESCO leases PV panels and takes responsibility for finance, installation and maintenance: offering a solar tariff and dealing with the export agreements [23]. Heat-as-a-service models sign consumers to a comfort agreement and can operate with district heat network with gas or biomass CHP or by installing heat pumps, again with ESCOs owning/leasing the infrastructure [24]. These models may even offer energy performance contracts for specified comfort levels for internal temperature, further incentivising efficiency in building fabric, lighting and appliances [25].

Sorrell and Steinberger et al’s seminal works on the economics of energy service contracts [25] and the potential of an energy performance based economy [26], provide a theoretical grounding for the study of these business models. Steinberger et al argued that a transition to a sustainable energy system must also involve a transition away from business models which rely on increasing ‘throughput’ sales of energy. Instead we must transition to a ‘performance based energy economy’, where profits are decoupled from energy consumption – leading to absolute reductions in demand. Sorrell further outlined how the economics and therefore economic viability of energy service business models is closely related to their associated transaction costs. Therefore, such contracts are only likely to be viable

when the *transaction costs* of implementing and negotiating an energy service contract can be outweighed by the energy *production cost* savings of efficiency measures and outsourcing to an ESCO. “Transaction costs, in turn, will be determined by the complexity of the energy service, the ‘specificity’ of the investments made by the contractor, the competitiveness of the energy services market and the relevant legal, financial and regulatory rules” [25].

Sorrell also defined energy service contracts by their *scope* –i.e. the number of energy streams covered by the contract (electricity, heating, cooling, hot water, lighting etc) and their *depth* –the extent to which the ESCO has control over final conversion equipment and therefore energy performance. As shown in Figure 1, shallower energy supply contracts involve the delivery of raw energy commodities whilst deeper performance contracts provide useful energy services - incentivising ESCOs to seek maximum efficiency from conversion equipment.

Figure 1 Energy service contracts: scope and depth. Adapted from Nolden and Sorrell (2016)

Historically, energy service contracts have been restricted to large public and industrial sites – due to these high transaction costs. A 2014/15 UK survey showed that the majority occur in the public sector, usually at larger sites such as hospitals and universities - often involving a combined heat and power (CHP) unit and the provision of heating, hot water and electricity [22]. However, more recently, examples in the residential sector have begun to emerge [27]. RENESCO in the Baltic states, ICF habitat in France and Bristol Energy in the UK are beginning to offer ‘pay for performance’ in the provision of thermal comfort in homes [27]. Further, the Energiesprong initiative has deep retrofitted several thousand homes in the Netherlands, bundling rooftop solar with multiple energy services including thermal comfort, hot water lighting and appliance use into 30 year net-zero energy performance

contracts with social housing providers [28]. Smartklub are also trialling sophisticated electricity market participation from rooftop solar systems and a grid connected battery as part of new build housing.

Several factors are contributing to the growing viability of these business models. Firstly, a range of intermediary organisations are helping to reduce associated transaction costs, through standardised contracts and procurement frameworks [29]. Secondly, the profusion of smart appliances, monitoring and machine learning are helping prospective ESCOs to reduce the costs of implementing and maintaining such contracts - also helping to reduce the risk of a performance gap [30]. Equally, as electricity markets become more decentralised, 'prosumer business models' are increasingly opening up new revenue streams - allowing ESCOs to 'stack' revenues and improve their underlying business case [31]. These developments present a prescient moment to explore the potential contribution of these business models to the decarbonisation of residential buildings. The following section sets out our methodology for this report including the stakeholder workshop with Smartklub, Bristol Energy and Energiesprong.

2. Methodology

This document draws on a series of background interviews and workshops across the UK, EU and USA conducted between 2016-2019, including several energy service business model cases notably: RENESCO in Latvia and the Baltic states; ICF habitat in France; Energies POSIT'IF in Paris; Energiesprong in the UK and Netherlands; Bristol Energy Company and Smartklub in the UK.

Three further focus groups in the city of Bristol aimed to unpack these issues and focus on the specific challenges at a city scale. The events brought together a diversity of stakeholders including local government, community energy organisations, businesses, citizens, academia and the third sector. The first workshop (June 11th, 2019), explored the challenges and opportunities facing prosumer business models in Bristol in a post-subsidy landscape – captured in a report [32]. A second roundtable (November 21st, 2019) focussed on the challenges of developing financing models using a community municipal bond structure, being developed by Bristol City Council. A third workshop (December 6th, 2019) delivered jointly with Bristol Energy Company focussed on the challenges of developing domestic energy service business models.

The energy as a service workshop involved a plenary session with three speakers – Bristol Energy Company, Energiesprong UK and Smartklub from the Nottingham Trent Basin project. Each speaker provided an outline of the business model as well as key pitfalls and challenges they were facing. Subsequently, the workshop was split into three groups each focussing on a different sector that might be addressed by energy service business models:

- New build housing
- Zero carbon heat
- Deep/whole house retrofit

Each group was asked to complete a ‘Business Model Canvas’ (Figure 2), outlining the potential features energy service business models for each respective sector. The Business Model Canvas provides a template for developing/documenting business models using nine building blocks. These can be simplified into four key elements describing the *value proposition*, *supply chain*, *customer interface*, and *financial model*, a fifth *governance* element describes the management and co-ordination of the other elements as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The business model canvas. (Brown 2019, adapted from Osterwalder and Pigneur 2010)

Finally, the group was asked to focus on specific opportunities and challenges for energy service business models for their respective sector. Respondents reflected on the challenges and opportunities of these business models from the perspectives of five key actor groups:

- Household/landlord
- Developers/SMEs
- Energy Suppliers
- Energy regulators
- Local/ Central Government

3. Findings from workshop

The examples discussed in the workshop varied in terms of their *scope* - with one group focussing on a single energy vector of heat provision, and the other two focussed on multiple vectors and the potential of total energy management. There was also debate on the *depth* of contract: as to whether true energy performance contracts for thermal comfort could be possible in a domestic setting, and the viability and complexity of demand side management and direct load control. This range of options and the potential relationship between different actors and the wider energy system is shown in Figure 3. Different models were seen to engage with these elements in different ways, with some having greater involvement with the wider electricity system, energy supplier and aggregators. The detailed findings and the business model canvases produced for each sector are provided in the following sections.

Legend

Electricity	
Payments	
Heat	
Ancillary/Flexibility Service	
Energy Services	

Figure 3 Generic Energy as a Service Business Model

3.1 New build energy service contracts

Energy service contracts in new build housing would fundamentally alter the housebuilding model of the UK. Currently, the majority of homes are built by speculative developers who take little or no interest once homes are built. This disincentivises investment in energy efficiency and other low carbon energy measures, as developers seek to reduce capital costs wherever possible. This lack of accountability for

energy performance is also a major driver of the pervasive ‘performance gap’ which plagues modern housebuilding.

Proponents argue through energy service contracts, developers could be contractually obliged to meet the standards to which homes were designed. Further, by involving an ESCO at an early stage - who would be responsible for ongoing energy service provision – developers would be compelled by the ESCO to ensure maximum efficiency and carbon reductions through their design, fabric specification, HVAC and onsite renewables. Equally, developers and ESCOs could merge their activities to offer *design, build and operate* contracts and could offer a single service charge for comfort, appliance use and lighting. Figure 4, summarises the potential features of these business models as developed in the workshop.

Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Owner occupiers <hr/> <p>Model must work for developer & ESCo</p>				
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer energy bills – one off cost and lock in or monthly payment plan (higher cost) • Electricity grid services • Renewable Heat Incentive Payments • Export PPA or Smart Guarantee <p>To suit customer needs</p>				

Figure 4 New build ESCO Business Model Canvas

In the UK, SmartKlub are trailing this model in the Trent Basin project. The project features a large PV array, 2.1MW battery, rooftop solar and groundsource heat pump connected to a district heat network. Smartklub have created an ESCO which manages the system and ensures optimal delivery of energy services with limited involvement from the prosumers/residents. Residents receive a reliable power and heat supply with the ESCO optimising the system to secure the best revenues and balance between import and export. Unlike Energiesprong and Bristol Energy, Smartklub do not offer comfort guarantees. However, using their large battery they are contracting into flexibility markets through an aggregator for additional revenues. Profits from the ESCO are recycled into a community fund, whilst the ESCO itself is designed to pass into community ownership at the end of the trial phase.

3.2 Low carbon heat as a service

Heat as a service models have the potential to address the major challenge of heat decarbonisation in homes. The majority of homes in the UK are heated using fossil fuels, predominantly gas boilers, with a similar pattern in other EU countries. Historically, households have purchased units of fuel (gas, oil, electricity) to heat their homes and have taken responsibility for the efficiency and maintenance of the conversion equipment themselves (boilers, heat controls, radiators). However, the need to decarbonise domestic heating means these high carbon systems must be converted to low carbon sources such as heat pumps and heat networks in the coming decades. This has presented a problem in many existing homes, where the high cost of infrastructure and equipment combined with different features such as lower flow temperatures and new controls has presented a barrier to uptake [33].

Heat as a service models may present a solution by providing households with the useful end service – a thermally comfortable home – and bundling the control/optimisation and financing of these higher CAPEX but lower running cost systems upstream into a single service payment. Such models are already more common in continental Europe, often involving heat networks and the delivery of centrally produced hot water through an ESCO. However, deeper contracts are emerging where customers enter into a ‘comfort tariff’: in effect paying for the temperature or comfort levels in specific rooms in the home. Equally, as electric heat pumps become more prevalent, ESCOs may also introduce smart heating control and storage systems – taking advantage of variations in the daily electricity price – to maximise revenues whilst ensuring the same comfort and service. It is hoped that customer centric ‘servitised’ heat offerings will reduce barriers to the adoption of low carbon heat systems. During the workshop these issues were explored largely in the context of existing homes, with the key elements of this business model presented in Figure 5.

<p>Key Partners </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Segment customers by values • “uptown elite” owner occupiers - Longevity barrier due to upfront costs • Early adopters • Social housing tenants • Rented - Big challenge due to focus on maximising returns 				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer ‘comfort payment plans – depending on levels of convenience? • Interest on financing of assets • Margins on electricity & assets • Sticky customers 				

Figure 5 Low carbon heat as a service business model canvas

Bristol Energy are exploring this business model and its potential for overcoming the dual challenges of high energy bills and climate change. During their trial of the 'heat-as-a-service' model, homeowners are offered a flat rate tariff based on the internal temperature of their home. Through a series of energy monitoring devices, the trial aims to generate data on occupant behaviour and heating system operation, for future refinement of the offering. The long-term objective is to reduce household expenditure through energy efficiency and the introduction of low carbon heat sources such as ASHPs. Here an improvement in occupant health and wellbeing is seen on an equal footing with energy savings. Consequently, local authorities and not for profit providers may be interested heat as a service business models – due to their greater emphasis on distributional benefits, social value and public good objectives.

3.3 Deep retrofit energy service contracts

For many homes, there is a need not only to install low carbon heat systems, but also invasive energy efficiency measures, alongside electricity microgeneration systems, smart controls and even home batteries. Indeed, the sheer size of the UK's domestic heat demand, will necessitate absolute reductions in energy demand if a significant share of this heat is to be electrified [33]. Further, many of the UK's homes are not suitable for lower temperature heat pumps and therefore efficiency improvements are an essential pre-requisite to heat decarbonisation. Although some incremental improvements to the UK's housing stock have been implemented, many of these low hanging fruit have now been exploited [34]. What remains are millions of insulated solid walls, floors and single glazed windows. This 'deep retrofit' challenge is therefore among the most beguiling of all decarbonisation goals. Increasingly, policymakers and practitioners are looking to energy service business models as a potential route to overcoming this challenge [35].

Although basic energy service models for district heat provision are common for large public sector or commercial sites¹, more comprehensive deep retrofit service models are growing in the UK, France and Netherlands. These models build on the principle of the 'heat-as-a-service' business models, but include building fabric efficiency measures, new HVAC systems and electricity microgeneration to provide a full 'energy-as-a-service' offering. These ideas were explored through a business model canvas shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Deep retrofit service contract business model canvas

The Energiesprong initiative is a deep retrofit program where homes are given a ‘net zero’ makeover which includes a new exterior shell, microgeneration, new heating and heating controls. Over a 30 year contract the ESCO guarantees the performance of the building, energy bills stay constant but the householder has an improved exterior appearance and internal building health. Savings on the energy bill pay back a large proportion of the investment over 30 years. This model has been successful in the Netherlands where costs per home have reduced by focusing on uniform social housing and working with local governments and other housing providers. The key benefits for the household are framed in terms of comfort and aesthetic improvement, while housing providers can significantly reduce maintenance costs, improve tenant retention and address occupant health and wellbeing issues. Thus far, these models (including the Energiesprong and RENESCO examples), have been tried in higher density and social housing units. As discussed, the high transaction costs of these contracts are considered to be a greater barrier to their adoption in single dwellings and for owner occupiers.

4. Challenges and opportunities for further adoption.

The canvassing exercise yielded a number of discussion points on challenges and opportunities for energy service business models, which are summarised against the elements of the business model below.

4.1 Value proposition

1. Two key discussion points were both the depth and scope of the energy service contract

2. The new build group discussed a shallower contract for hot water and electricity rather than comfort or appliance services, although included a broader scope of energy services and the option of providing efficient appliances and also demand side management. This would allow buyers to purchase smart appliances off plan from developers
3. However, the deep retrofit model based on the Energiesprong initiative involves a deeper energy performance contract and comfort plan
4. Evidence from the Netherlands suggests that these performance contracts are easier to implement in a new build context – due to controlled conditions
5. The heat as a service group explored a deeper comfort proposition although discussed the energy performance risk this brings without installing measures to the building fabric. This model was predicated on providing decarbonised heat, energy and comfort as an individual offer i.e. not an area based approach and assumes the energy service companies are licensed energy suppliers.
6. However, due to the requirements of 28 day supplier switching, offering a long term service contract is currently easier if the asset lease/finance is provided separately from the energy supply contract
7. Although an important aspect is potential property value increases, there is currently little evidence of a market premium. Approaches such as Energiesprong are also predicated on an aesthetic improvement leading to increased value – although this element is subjective
8. Finally, signing energy utility contracts over longer periods needs to become normal but is counter to the current narrative of switching often.

4.2 Customer interface

1. Targeting customers was viewed as a challenge by all groups
2. Historically, low carbon housing and deeper retrofits have been adopted by an ‘uptown elite’ of owner occupiers, therefore there are challenges in reaching a wider market
3. It was discussed by the heat as a service group that targeting customers on the basis of ‘values’ such as concerns around climate change and energy poverty could be an important first market, rather than a ‘mass marketing approach’
4. The new build group identified owner occupiers as a crucial first market, despite energy service charges being more common in the private and social rented sector
5. They also discussed how service contracts could be sold through the developer with a preferred ESCO to take on the contract
6. Private landlords were identified as a major barrier by all groups with stronger legislation needed in this area
7. A further issue was how to disincentivise energy profligacy from residents who are on a flat performance contract – Energiesprong have tried to solve this with quotas for heat and appliance usage – SmartKlub share the ESCOs revenues among residents disincentivising waste
8. Energiesprong has thus far only worked in social housing with private rented and owner occupiers much more difficult in part to fewer scale economies
9. In general, there is a lack of demand for and trust in electric heating and electric cooking. Confidence comes from trials.
10. Even with the Energiesprong rapid install process, there remains significant disruption for residents which presents a major barrier to uptake

4.3 Supply Chain

1. For new build models, developers need ESCOs to work with them in the design phase - eventually some may look to integrate their activities
2. It needs to be clear what happens if the ESCO goes bust (no supplier of last resort able to take on ESCO contracts yet). There should be some community or communal knowledge role. What are the right KPIs to apply and monitor against? Who do you call if it [heat pump etc] goes wrong?
3. Construction SMEs often have a full workload of conventional property upgrades will not move into this new market until it is clear that there is a market in place
4. If there were a healthy sector of companies it would be possible to switch between ESCOs with guaranteed service levels
5. However, there is currently a huge skills gap and much poor quality workmanship – especially in the retrofit space
6. If ESCOs and Energy Suppliers are to integrate their activities there remains a need to get smart metering data right, and to improve and standardise monitoring and evaluation
7. Also, ESCOs may struggle to access to the electricity wholesale, balancing and ancillary markets – there is also needed to import grid electricity - necessitating a relationship with a licenced supplier

4.4 Financial model

1. A crucial element to all of the business models was affordable finance, although different forms of finance are more or less suitable for alternative sectors and tenures
2. In new build the obvious starting point is mortgage financing – meaning developers would charge a higher purchase price
3. Mortgage providers can reduce interest with guaranteed energy performance as they face less risk as house values increase and energy and maintenance outgoings reduce
4. Trust: if the mortgage company provides green loans there is a need for monitoring, reporting and evaluation that communicates outcomes clearly
5. Alternatively, measures can be funded through ongoing service charge or on energy bills – this is likely to be the route for retrofitted heat and insulation solutions
6. For this segment new low interest finance mechanisms are needed – other countries have solved this issue through publicly subsidised low interest loans
7. Due to the supplier switching issue, it is currently easier to offer asset financing as a separate lease, rather than bundle into the energy bill of a supply contract – however the Green Deal's repayment mechanism is also an option that could be explored
8. Either way, this repayment should stay with the home – not the individual
9. Private finance providers are likely to need scale and be able to aggregate and securitise multiple loans for sale into secondary markets
10. Without this, some form of government backed low cost finance is likely to be needed – much like what occurs in Germany

5. Key stakeholders

Each group was then asked to contemplate the opportunities and challenges of energy service business models from the perspective of key stakeholder groups: **households/landlords, developers/SME contractors; energy suppliers and energy regulators** – shown in Table 1. This exercise demonstrated that many of these issues were commonly held between the different sectors, although in general there

seemed to be fewer barriers in new build housing and the most for deep retrofit models – suggesting that such models should be trialled initially in a new build context.

Table 1 Opportunities and challenges for energy service models - stakeholder perspectives

Issue		New Build	Low Carbon Heat	Deep Retrofit
Household / landlord 	Higher purchase price of homes	✓		
	High CAPEX of measures			✓
	New concept and is poorly understood	✓	✓	✓
	Concerns over behaviour change and expectations	✓		✓
	Customer concerns over ESCO lock into service contracts/ comfort plans	✓	✓	✓
	Risk of tenant disruption/dissatisfaction		✓	✓
	Ease of organizing access/ getting agreement		✓	✓
	Space needed for new equipment		✓	✓
	Special finance needed		✓	✓
	Long payback demands preferential interest rates or tax breaks			✓
	Major disruption to occupants necessitates speed			✓
	Landlords concerns around voids and losses - can be addressed through a demonstrated return and tax discount			✓
	Developer/ contractors 	Significant performance risk of measures		✓
Lack of local/regional offsite manufacturing capability & supply chain to support the local economy		✓		✓
Accreditation and training of SME contractors to standards and design		✓	✓	✓
SMEs too busy full order books already – lack of capacity			✓	✓
Inconsistent demand, uncertainty of pipeline			✓	✓
Annual service contracts needed – not necessarily available		✓	✓	✓

	Issues with condition of housing stock and unsuitability for HPs – who shoulders risk if system goes wrong?		✓	✓
	Cooperative models could be a benefit	✓	✓	✓
	Developers: No long-term interest in creating a future proofed home	✓		
	Developer needs to identify an ESCO to take on the guarantee or take on themselves	✓		
Energy Supplier 	Reduced energy consumption reduces income for suppliers	✓		✓
	Domestic ESCOs present radical change of supplier business model – move away from energy sales to service - move away from vertical integration	✓	✓	✓
	Customer choice and churn hampers long term models	✓	✓	✓
	Needs a competitive retrofit ESCo sector with transferable assets and good lines of consumer credit and access to debit	✓	✓	✓
	New metering requirements – smart meters not enough	✓	✓	✓
	Big data management value creation – hampered by data compatibility issues	✓	✓	✓
	Potential for revenue stacking from domestic flexibility	✓	✓	✓
	Financing dimension currently necessitates separation between ESCO and energy supplier		✓	✓
Regulator 	Regulation needed to assign roles and responsibilities & liabilities to: Developer, ESCO, Management Company & Community Group	✓	✓	✓
	Need liquid/competitive market	✓	✓	✓
	ESCO failure – need regulated ESCO of last resort	✓	✓	✓
	Lack of ESCO accreditation	✓	✓	✓
	Network Charging DSUOS – Need virtual private wires using common infrastructure	✓		✓
	Offering consumer protection for comfort is problematic – what is the metric/standard?	✓	✓	✓
	Building Regulations not designed for performance outcomes	✓		✓

6. Policy recommendations

Finally, the workshop participants developed a series of policy recommendations for local and national governments which could facilitate the increased adoption of domestic energy service business models. These recommendations are summarised below.

General

- Govt. should develop a 20 year decarbonisation plan and skills program for the low carbon construction sector – emphasising performance and actual outcomes
- Carbon prices would also help to make energy prices more reflective of the underlying carbon content of energy supply – this would benefit low carbon and decentralised sources
- Legislation surrounding supplier switching is being strengthened in the EU Clean Energy Package, and switching times are to reduce to as little as 24 hours. This legislation disincentivises long term supply contracts and hampers energy suppliers offering these contracts. BREXIT could present an opportunity to review this logic.
- New regulation is needed to manage the domestic ESCO market and to protect consumers from lock in
- Supplier of last resort is needed to take on ESCO contracts

New Build

- Govt. should introduce performance based compliance through Part L – of the Building regulations
- Alternatively, developers could be required to meet similar standards through local planning policy
- Govt. should do more to develop Green Mortgage market and regulate it effectively
- Electricity network charges (DSUOS and TNUOS) should be cost reflective using virtual private networks

Low carbon heat

- National/Regional strategic plan on heat decarbonisation needed
- Moratorium on fossil heat in new build should be extended to all homes
- Policy costs on electricity bills unfairly prejudice electrification – these costs should be shifted into general taxation to level the playing field away from gas
- Barriers for domestic participation in flexibility markets should be removed

Deep Retrofit

- Minimum energy efficiency standards (MEES) at point of sale or rent needed to develop long term retrofit strategy
- Planning policy surrounding permitted development needs amendment to facilitate solid wall and façade upgrades
- Fiscal incentives such as reduced VAT, Stamp Duty and Council tax needed to improve underlying financial case
- Performance based retrofit in local authority social housing could be first step to wider performance contracts becoming mainstream
- Govt. backed Low cost finance and grant funding for fuel poor essential for deep retrofit strategy

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